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CALIBRATION AND PERFORMANCE OPTIMIZATION OF pH AND TURBIDITY SENSORS FOR EMBEDDED WATER SYSTEMS

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Accurate calibration of pH and turbidity sensors is vital for maintaining the precision and reliability of low-cost, automated water treatment systems. However, open-source sensors commonly suffer from nonlinear response, signal drift, and environmental sensitivity, which limit their long-term measurement stability. This study presents a systematic calibration and validation approach for gravity analog pH and turbidity sensors integrated within an Arduino-driven water system. The calibration mechanism was designed as a button-triggered, five-step routine that activates under user command. The process involves three successive button presses to record analog voltage outputs in standard reference solutions pH 4.00, 7.00, and 10.00, for pH calibration, and Formazin standards of 25, 100, and 200 NTU for turbidity calibration, followed by automatic generation of a linear regression model to determine calibration coefficients. A fourth step saves these coefficients temporarily in the Arduino Nano's memory, while a fifth step initiates real-time readings updated every 20 seconds. A dedicated reset button allows recalibration when drift or measurement deviation is detected, ensuring continuous accuracy. The regression models demonstrated strong linearity. When compared with commercial reference meters, the calibrated sensors achieved mean percentage errors of 4.13% for pH and 2.85% for turbidity, both within the accepted analytical tolerance of $\pm 5\%$. Multi-cycle testing confirmed minimal signal variation and stable sensor performance. Moreover, the proposed methodology is broadly applicable to other analog-output water quality sensors, such as ORP, conductivity, dissolved oxygen, and total dissolved solids probes, where parameter voltage relationships can be expressed through linear or polynomial regression. This adaptability positions the framework as a generalized calibration strategy for improving accuracy, stability, and long-term reliability in embedded environmental monitoring and automated water systems.

Keywords: Sensor calibration, Linear regression, Arduino Microcontroller, pH and turbidity sensors, Measurement accuracy